

Mathematical concepts and methodological dilemmas: Research on the movement of thought and body

Mamta Naik, Manchester Metropolitan University, ✉ m.naik@mmu.ac.uk

This paper explores some of the methodological dilemmas that emerge when researching mathematics learning processes with pre-service elementary teachers, whilst focusing on the genetic and material dimensions of mathematical concepts. Case study data from a project situated in a UK University is used to help elaborate and unravel these dilemmas. The discussion focuses on recent writing about the nature of mathematical concepts, merging philosophical, sociological and cognitive perspectives, with the aim of unpacking the complex ways in which 'movement' of thought and body plays a pivotal role.

Introduction

This paper seeks to explore the methodological implications which arose when I sought to engage in research with elementary pre-service teachers, where I aimed to encourage them to step out of the known, the familiar, and the learned, to bring forth an 'inventive' and 'speculative' dimension to their thinking about the nature of mathematical concepts. Although many other researchers have pursued kindred aims, under the general rubric of 'constructivist learning', my own conviction was that creative speculation in mathematics demanded leaving the secure fold of established and respected theoretical frameworks and methodological paradigms for mathematics education research, and the need to venture further afield into ontological considerations from within the philosophy of mathematics.

The context for the research is a UK teacher education program where elementary teachers are trained for mathematics teaching; and although these future teachers arrive with plenty of cultural capital and insight into children and learning, they are ill-prepared to dive into complex texts about classical philosophical questions like: what is a mathematical concept? What is the nature of mathematics? They are more readily attuned to sociological and psychoanalytic theories of socio-cultural identity, which is a mainstay of the education training at the institution, furnishing them with strong insights into the political framing of education. And they are equally handy with constructivist theories of learning, which are also a mainstay, whereby the common-sense notion that learning should be student-centred, collaborative and emerge through a process of discovery resonates with their intuited notions of childhood education, often gained through their own 'apprenticeship' of (mathematics) education (Lortie, 2002). Despite the fact that such learning theories implicitly

Please cite as: Naik, M. (2021). Mathematical concepts and methodological dilemmas: Research on the movement of thought and body. In D. Kolloosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 2, pp. 689–698). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5415604>

carry philosophical assumptions about the nature of mind, body and concept, it remains very challenging for most of us to philosophically engage directly with the specificity of mathematical practices and concepts. We can train teachers to problematize ‘mathematics education’ but the aim here is the more challenging prospect of problematizing *mathematics itself on its own terms*.

With that in mind, this paper discusses how attempts were made with participants of this research study, to explore the question: what is a mathematical concept? This discussion and exploration of mathematical concepts from a more philosophical perspective, will be enriched through engagement with some recent compelling approaches, and a discussion of how the ideas of posthumanist philosopher Karen Barad might help us to open up teacher training in new directions. The paper explores how this approach is able to support the means to awaken the student teachers’ possibility to re-imagine fundamental mathematical concepts in new ways, and to think more radically about how inventive, generative and speculative habits and practices are actually the *ontological* source of mathematical concepts. In embracing the opportunities this provides for all involved, I re-turn to the learning of geometrical mathematical concepts at the elementary phase of schooling, and document Barad’s (2007) inherent demand for a fundamental re-working of ontology and epistemology to align with the ethical and thus implications for methodology within the research process. This will involve assessing the implications of such an approach to mathematics education, along with challenges which ensue in taking up a posthumanist theoretical framework in research in this area. I will use some data from a case study to help elaborate the possibilities such a framework offers, which may not be so evident through aforementioned pedagogical frameworks which are underpinned by commonly established and recognisable theories. I will also unpack the methodological dilemmas/challenges that emerge while working with pre-service teachers in this vein. I focus on the concept of circle, and share data where pre-service teachers encountered circles as socio-material events, emphasizing the dynamic and genetic matter-concept mixture that was in process during the events.

What is a mathematical concept?

To unfold this discussion, I will firstly share some recent compelling theoretical approaches to the question of ‘what is a mathematical concept?’ Each offers fresh insights, which range from the social construction of concepts; the role of the body in concept-development, to anthropological and ecological approaches.

According to Barwell and Abtahi (2017) language and wider discourses through “thoughts, ideas, mental representations” (p. 178) operate to define what ‘concept’ is within mathematics. They expose a fascinating polarised binary produced within dominant discourses within the Canadian (British Columbian) media where a dichotomy of ‘back to basics’ and ‘discovery’ (investigative) learning is produced, where ‘concept’ becomes objectified within the latter through mediated representations of what mathematical concepts are. Through an embodied cognition enactivist approach, Coles (2017), aims to

attend to the ecological as more than purely language-based, and carries a prime focus on mathematical concepts as relational, with particular attention to similarities, differences, and comparisons. These are not seen as determinate; they are always produced through acting on discernible relations and differences within an event or encounter rather than on a mediated representation or awareness of objects.

Coles (2017) moves away from an object-oriented approach where for example, a child might label (through the use of language) individual objects within a set, whilst developing understanding of early number concepts. For Coles (2017), a move away from such a 'counting world' with an emphasis on concepts as fixed objects towards one which attends to mathematical concepts as 'relations', enables a move to a 'measurement world' after Bass (2015, cited by Coles, 2017). Through an embodied encounter, the concept, for example the cardinality of number, can be brought forth through a relational encounter. An example Coles (2017) gives, is the use of Cuisenaire rods, with each different colour representing a different proportionate length. When two or more different coloured rods are physically placed together, this embodied act enacts a naturally occurring comparison, through a focus on the relationship. Here, number is perceived not as a collection of objects but as a "dynamic relation". Numbers are brought into existence through the action of placing rods against each other. There is some sense of production or generation, and through a relational perspective, it may also be suggestive of a sense of 'indeterminacy'. What this does is to move away from purely linguistic practices and moves to focus on mathematical practices which through the relational is folded into a complex material milieu.

Through enactivist embodiment, Coles (2017) desires to challenge the classical divide between subject-object or knower and known through the phenomenon which produces the mathematical concept or relation. However, he does acknowledge that this is difficult, as we are often inherently grounded in a binary between knower and known, something which can be seen operating within the earlier example of the mediated mathematical 'concept' as highlighted by Barwell and Abtahi (2017). In order to surmount this, Coles (2017) turns to the use of illusions, in the tradition of Maturana, a key enactivist thinker. Here, the phenomenon requires a consideration of context, as well as the relations that are borne out of it. Objects can only be perceived through their relationships, thus in this way concepts are treated as objects here. There is a suggestion of subject and object being seen as emerging out of each other therefore there may be some sense of a commingling. Specifically, for Coles (2017, p. 221) "Relations are at once material (arising from a consideration of objects) and abstract." They are not seen to exist in the objects or in the human mind. These relations, thus 'concepts' arise from the interactions of the human with the world and each other.

For Nemirovsky (2017), taking an anthropological turn highlights the inherent nature of the mathematical concept as being multi-faceted and situated in material practices. He critiques the classic Aristotelian image of 'concept' through a 'classification' model of predicates, already essentialised, and with a lack of historicity, thus knowledge of production. Furthermore, he suggests a nature/culture binary is produced through "taxonomies driven

by relations of power and enforcements” (pp. 252–253) where anything falling between essentialised boundaries is afforded lower status. Nemirovsky moves away from this static, classification model and offers instead the crystalline image of ‘concept’ as that which is “inspired by growth, decay and individuation” (p. 253). For Nemirovsky, this means concepts are always under formation; they are relational, always in consort with something else and of the material. In doing so, he foregrounds both the potentiality of the senses; i.e. a concept meshes all the senses of a virtual. Nemirovsky is also drawing on Deleuze here, to argue that the virtual alludes to a non-deterministic “footprinting” of a multitude of possibilities. This idea of meshing suggests something beyond a mere linkage of ideas within concept-formation. Through the work of Ingold (2015), Nemirovsky invites us to question the rigidity and determinate nature of mathematical concepts, and to address their historicity through attention to the multitude of relational ways in which they might have been formed.

De Freitas and Sinclair (2014, 2017) operate within a posthumanist and specifically ‘Inclusive Materialist’ framework, which draws on key Baradian ideas. They are committed to concepts as “aesthetic-political” acts and similarly to Nemirovsky, are particularly keen to avoid traditional notions of mathematical concepts as being static, essentialised and inanimate, set apart from our physical world, to be unproblematically ‘discovered’. This is part of an agenda to show how concepts live in the world, and to avoid a “double-standard ontology” (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2017, p. 76). They consider how concepts are often linked within mathematics by way of logical connectives; the pervasive act of “ordering” mathematical concepts based on a ‘logical’ sequence within school curricula can however be challenged, once we start problematizing concepts. De Freitas and Sinclair (2014, 2017) draw on the work of Gilles Châtelet to present several propositions about mathematical concepts. In contrast to Barwell and Abtahi (2017), they problematise the idea of ‘concepts’ as metaphors, representations or mental constructs abstracted from the material world (where abstraction might be treated as a subtraction of nuisance or secondary qualities). For de Freitas and Sinclair, the discussion of ‘abstract’ concepts carries an ontological challenge, one where concepts connect with both the virtual and the actual within an immanent world without transcendent ideal mathematical forms.

Within the framework of Inclusive Materialism, the active and yet undetermined ‘virtual’ is imbued within matter, as multiplicities of what de Freitas and Sinclair (2017) call ‘quivering’ or indeterminate potentialities, any one of which can result in an instantiation through the actualisation that occurs from the latency within the matter. This latency is not an essentialised mathematical form within or of the matter, but rather the mathematical concept is always becoming through “the mobility, vibration, potentiality and indeterminacy” (p. 78).

My interest is in how these approaches are helpful for working closely with mathematical concepts and adult learners training to become elementary teachers; each draws attention to material-mathematical practices and to indeterminacy. I am working with a theoretical framework that is kindred with those that have been discussed above and case study data will now be explored through this milieu.

Concepts as apparatus

I work with the ideas of philosopher of science Karen Barad on ‘Agential Realism’ (2007) where concepts arise from specific material arrangements. Barad invokes the reader to engage with an epistemological-ontological-ethical framework (Barad, 2007, p. 26), where the ethical and “response-ability” is considered within all aspects of the research process. This results in an inherent demand for a fundamental re-working of the traditional framing of ontology and epistemology, where the ethical is brought into play and the material is afforded agency. Along with methodology, each are equally imbricated within an ‘ethically’ oriented entanglement. For Barad (2003), these entanglements are material arrangements or apparatus; I work within this framework to develop the idea of the ‘mathematical body’. This is created through an assemblage which specifies a distinct material arrangement, one which is relational, contingent on the actors in the assemblage, within the becoming of a new mixture of concept and matter. By actors, this means a diverse set of agents, human and otherwise - the human, the compass, the straight edge, as well as the concept itself as a configuration of forces. This aligns with Barad’s theoretical stance that ‘agency’ for all actors, human and non-human, is produced through the becoming of the ‘concept’; therefore, unlike for Coles (2017), where the human ‘interacts’ and acts upon the material, agency for Barad (2007) is not pre-invested in any of the actors prior to the assemblage in its becoming.

My approach aligns with those previously discussed, specifically in an attempt to think more broadly about concept formation, and one where the human is to be decentred. As Coles (2017) notes, philosophically, and methodologically, this can be difficult as it creates a deeply ontological challenge. The following discussion of data attempts to explore some of these complexities.

Case study data: The circle de/composed

From a methodological perspective, as a researcher whose research contexts have always consisted of classrooms, which are fully involved with doings and not just sayings, it seemed natural to make the move from the comfort of socio-cultural paradigms where much research relies on standard observation protocols, or the common employment of interviews and questionnaires as research tools. As well as from the demands of allegiance to a qualitative and often interpretative inquiry paradigm, where that which is the “social” and of ‘knowing’ through language is taken for granted. Those researching beyond qualitative inquiry paradigms, such as de Freitas and Sinclair (2014) and Barad (2003, 2007) offer a particular challenge to the in-built Cartesian dualism which gives precedence to mind over body within much education research. They argue such inquiry can only ever be ‘representationalist’. Posthumanist philosophers challenge the lack of attention to the materiality of the human body itself as well as that of ‘more-than-human’ actors. (Barad, 2007; Coole & Frost, 2010).

The research project discussed here aimed to encourage pre-service trainee teachers to step out of the known and bring forth an ‘inventive’ and ‘speculative’ dimension to their thinking, perhaps to access an indeterminate potentiality through the virtual (de Freitas &

Sinclair, 2014; Nemirovsky, 2017), and to crack open the very notion of circle and other concepts. In other words, concepts broke from the 'known properties' attached to the shape, as static onto-assumptions about their essential quality, and became unfolding events, which were dynamically involved in the becoming of concepts. Together, we tried to attend to that which was eclipsed by language-use in learning, which might have otherwise hindered our capacity to leave behind deeply entrenched existing ontological and epistemological assumptions. Barad's requirement to work within an epistemological-ontological-ethical framework demands all elements to be ethically considered as an imbricated whole; this results in a fundamental shift in thinking, where methodology is not a separate and distinct feature of the research process, of already fixed and pre-determined means guided by a research paradigm with 'already decided' apparatus which perceives already existent concept(s). That would typically suggest engagement in empirical acts where the concept is supposedly brought forth, to be discovered/recognized by the learner in this tried and tested constructivist way.

However, to work within Barad's theoretical framework, it is necessary to think with the onto-epistemology; where no boundaries exist between the theory and the methodology for Barad, and her theory of 'agential realism' encounters concepts in experimental apparatus and design through a realisation of this framework. Hers is an attempt to better engage with the force of the conceptual on the plane of the material, and vice versa. Barad's attention, as a philosopher of science, shifts from purely discursive practices to apparatuses as material-discursive practices, and attention to the importance of experiments where concept-matter mixtures mutate over time. For Barad, Physics philosopher Bohr designs experiments of consequential significance, whereby concepts and apparatus commingle (de Freitas, 2017). These are also experiments through which the very distinction between the social and scientific, culture and nature is constituted. Therefore, method and theory cannot consist only of general epistemological schemes underpinned by beliefs grounded in 'mediation' between language and object but must grapple with the aberrant dynamic movement of thought-matter, incorporating the singular complexities inherent in this kind of eco-sophical development (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2014).

In taking up the call of Barad (2007) to examine complex activities for how they reach outside of language, and to take up her theoretical approach of agential realism, I sought to engage in 'teaching design experiments' as a methodological approach. The first and unfortunately misguided staging post on this journey, was to fold in the body to recognise its capacity for cognisance as this offered some scope to further consider the empirical acts which might create access to spaces where students might leave behind old and worn pre-conceived ideas about their understandings of the nature of mathematical concepts as fixed objects mediated through metaphors or language (Coles, 2017; de Freitas & Sinclair, 2017). For research purposes, I hoped this would open up more-than-human and more-than-discursive ways of doing mathematics; to harness the potential of the materials and their engagement with the physical and the material to surface relations, as promoted by Coles (2017). A series of activities were designed, which asked the students to engage in circle-

formations using a variety of media and importantly, their bodies. The activities were directed, instructional and though there was some scope for varying outputs, the focus was on the decomposition of circles. I had a realisation that this methodological approach did not align with the call by Barad (2007) to ‘speculate’, ‘generate’, ‘come into being’. The specific material arrangement or ‘apparatus’ ultimately centered the human learner, by necessity as having the agency to act upon inert matter in the manner of Coles (2017); but perhaps more importantly, these tasks were all decomposition tasks, so the circle was given in materiality, as much as it was given conceptually, and I realized I was still centering the familiar, known, and learned – the experiment was focused on decomposition rather than composition.

This was uncharted territory for me as researcher and although both de/composition tasks are helpful, I note that my Baradian tendency had me convinced that if I was to move into the realm of generativity and to enable the ‘becoming’ of circle, it was necessary to engage in a different way. That is, to listen to Barad’s call to move away from a relativist approach which inherently separates observer and observed, with the observer (invariably human) having privileged agency, thus challenge my still-entrenched human-centric view of ‘concept’. Viewing the ‘mathematical concept’ as an agentic actor produced through an intra-action required me to move this concept into a space of speculation and indeterminacy where the specific material arrangement or ‘apparatus’ required careful consideration. For Barad, ‘apparatus’ here is not to be seen as that which is independent of the observer (subject) and the observed (object); an independent measuring tool bridging a perceived ‘gap’ and mediating between the two. Here, the epistemological-ontological-ethical needed to be brought into play as all actors (human and non-human) are constituted through the ‘apparatus’ therefore this embroiled nature necessitated observer and observed becoming an integral part of the specific material arrangement or apparatus. It was not possible to think about any one of these aspects in isolation; this had clear methodological implications and implications for the production of and analysis of data within the research inquiry undertaken within this theoretical framework.

I needed to perhaps connect with Nemirovsky’s proposition (2017) to consider an approach akin to that of Ingold’s ‘wayfaring’, of one where concepts are made over time with no particular or determinate intent; they ‘become’ (2015). Or perhaps to think of the event of circle creation as one where virtual ‘singularities’ destabilize the making of circles in generative ways, so that the truly novel emerges. It was necessary for me to create teaching design experiments where mobility, creation and the ‘virtual’ had opportunities to come into being. The ‘virtual’ as a multiplicity of possibilities, in the vein of Chatelet’s promulgation (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2017), required a loosening of tutor direction and an opening up of playful and dynamic activity which harnessed the use of tools, environment as well as the unfinished human body, for production and generativity through the relational (Barad, 2003; de Freitas & Sinclair, 2014; Coles, 2017). A much less prescribed atmosphere where the students were asked no more than to produce what they conceived of as the concept of ‘circle’, with a wide variety of media freely available, yielded some interesting results.

Cracking open deeply established associations of exploration of circle as related to its (fixed and determinate) properties provided some striking results.

One such result involves Mimi. Mathematical objects operate according to logical constraints and ontological possibilities. In considering the circle, De Freitas and Sinclair (2017) focus on both an actualization of the virtual and a realization of the possible, which together yield 'new-ness'. The latter corresponds with a definition of 'circle' which satisfies the constraints of the locus of all points being equi-distant from its centre. This highlights how the requirement to abide by the onto/logical necessity of this definition demands compliance with a set of points which are determined by the constraints of the static nature of this definition. However, there is also another kind of determination, whose definition differs in that it is a dynamic one, and of the material rather than the logical. One which involves an actualizing of the virtual dimensions of the matter through the event of producing a continuous curve, one which involves action, mobility and thus generates. Mimi surprisingly engages with both these static and dynamic definitions. Firstly, she realizes the possible of 'circle' by conforming to the set of points determined by the constraints of being in relation to a fixed centre, through the creation of a circle-like figure by cutting out of folded paper and further continues in this vein by using the circumference of this paper circle-like figure to form a further string circle which is glued just inside the outer circumference. However, she then proceeds to create a circle which does not follow this onto/logical definition. She uses a length of string to work her way out from a central inside. In connecting with the growing 'area' of her circle, there is a material physicality and mobility imbricated fully within the string, paper and glue she works with or which perhaps works her; where the mathematical concept is 'becoming' through "...the mobility, vibration, potentiality and indeterminacy..." (de Freitas & Sinclair, 2017, p. 78) within the materiality of the forming circle. Mimi and her circle are produced through Barad's (2007, p. 147) 'field of possibilities' where statements and subjects emerge. Barad describes this field as being dynamic and full of contingent multiplicity. When asked how she produced the inner-circle, Mimi shrugs and ventures:

Mimi: I'm not really sure. I just started here (points to first point of string she has glued down in the centre) then just – I don't know, just went like this! (Traces a circular winding action with her right index finger in the air).

She does not say it but implies that the string led her on an ontological journey of 'newness' which even she did not know the map for – the concept of circle was new, not simply recollected or recognized. The point is not simply that she learned a new way of thinking about circles. My approach affirms that fact, but my turn to posthumanist theories opens up this event so that the very ontology of the concept is at stake. In other words, philosophically examining this activity through the lens of posthumanism, allows us to radicalize the way that mathematical concepts become concepts. In disrupting notions of agency and how this comes into being and for which actors within a specific material arrangement or apparatus (Barad, 2007), we are able to break up and destabilize institutional mathematics, allowing us

to critique curriculum. My posthumanist philosophical analysis puts Mimi into a much broader milieu of matter-concept mixtures, actually empowering her by looking more broadly. This journey relates to the 'inherent mobility within the circle' to which de Freitas and Sinclair (2017, p. 81) point. The circle is very much as they say 'materially produced'. Mimi's (inner) *circling event* eventually does result in the production of the form of circle; however, during production this is full of indeterminacy; the material is still within the 'virtual', quivering with a multitude of potentialities with all the possibilities this may bring for Baradian ontic-semantic boundaries within this specific material-discursive arrangement or apparatus.

Conclusion

Research focusing on the teaching of elementary level mathematics with student teachers is interesting and complex. These students come at once as enthusiastic apprentices (to the endeavour of teaching mathematics) and yet often strangely alienated from mathematics itself. Undertaking research focused on conceptual mathematics is a risky endeavour, given the affect and fear and the strong desires at work. For these reasons, I have sought alternative theoretical approaches and new kinds of experimental practices that would allow me to take up the many complex processes by which mathematical concepts become mathematical concepts.

If we wish for student (pre-service) teachers to engage with an ontological challenge such as this, we need to look to research to stimulate a professional conversation, where a more philosophical slant is brought into our teacher education programs. Conversations are needed which might open up and challenge deeply entrenched notions of the nature of mathematics as a discipline as well as the nature of mathematics as a curriculum subject, in order to challenge the essentialised taxonomies highlighted by Nemirovsky (2017). This may involve recognising that this is uncharted and at times difficult territory, where regulatory bodies with deeply-entrenched ontologies may need to be navigated. Furthermore, at a time when the current pandemic has at times disrupted the dominant grand narratives of socio-cultural theories by bringing into sharp focus and problematizing our dependence on language-focused pedagogies in online learning, there may be an appetite to return to questions about the materiality of mathematics pedagogy, and reconsider the ontological nature of mathematical concepts. Barad (2007) offers something distinctively different and appealing. However, hers is a highly theoretical framework and I continue to work on the personal challenge this presents to connect with research such as mine.

References

- Barad, K., (2003). Posthumanist performativity: Toward an understanding of how matter comes to matter. *Journal of Women in Culture and Society*, (28)3, 801–831
- Barad, K. (2007). *Meeting the universe halfway: Quantum physics and the entanglement of matter and meaning*. Duke University Press.

M. Naik

- Barwell, R., & Abtahi, Y. (2017). Mathematics concepts in the news. In E. de Freitas, N. Sinclair, & A. Coles (Eds.), *What is a mathematical concept?* (pp. 175–188). Cambridge University Press.
- Coles, A. (2017). A relational view of mathematical concepts. In E. de Freitas, N. Sinclair, & A. Coles (Eds.), *What is a mathematical concept?* (pp. 205–222). Cambridge University Press
- Coole, D., & Frost, S. (2010). *New materialisms: Ontology, agency, and politics*. Duke University Press.
- de Freitas, E. (2017). Karen Barad's quantum ontology and posthuman ethics: Rethinking the concept of relationality. *Qualitative Inquiry*, (23)9, 741–748.
- de Freitas, E., & Sinclair, N. (2014). *Mathematics and the body: Material entanglements in the classroom*. Cambridge University Press.
- de Freitas, E., & Sinclair, N. (2017). Concepts as generative devices. In E. de Freitas, N. Sinclair, & A. Coles (Eds.), *What is a mathematical concept?* (pp. 76–89). Cambridge University Press.
- Ingold, T. (2015). *The life of lines*. Routledge.
- Lortie, D. C. (2002). *Schoolteacher: A sociological study*. University of Chicago Press.
- Nemirovsky, R. (2017) Inhabiting mathematical concepts. In E. de Freitas, N. Sinclair, & A. Coles (Eds.), *What is a mathematical concept?* (pp. 125–142). Cambridge University Press.